

COMPARISON BETWEEN COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH DUE TO MICROBUCKLING AND KINKING IN FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The compressive strength of fibrous composites due to a localized kinking failure is evaluated. The modeling of kink propagation is undertaken using an energy principle, which predicts the necessary applied compressive load to sustain the kink propagation. Such modeling takes into account the macro-geometry of the composite structure as well as the micro-geometry in addition to material parameters. The effect of laminate geometry, lay-up configuration as well as the relation between kink initiation and kink propagation are studied. Since initial microbuckling has often been suggested as a precursor leading to a kinking failure mode, the predictions of a microbuckling analysis are compared with the compressive strength due to kinking for various composite systems.

KEYWORDS: Compressive Strength; Fibrous Composites; Kinking; Micro-Buckling.

1. INTRODUCTION

The strength of composites under compressive loading has been studied by many researchers in the past three decades. Experimental studies have been carried out to gain more understanding of the phenomenon and several different analytical models were proposed. The analytical approaches could be grouped into two main categories. The first one basically involves the study of microbuckling of fibers embedded in an elastic or elastoplastic matrix. The first models based on this approach were proposed by Schuerch (1964) and Rosen (1965). The second approach is to study localized failure in the form of a kink band. Examples of this approach are the models proposed by Argon (1972) and Budiansky (1983).

Microbuckling of fibers in composites was first observed by Dow and Gruntfest (1960) and later analyzed by Schuerch (1964, 1966) and independently by Rosen (1965) with similar results. The well known Rosen model considers a two-dimensional array of layers of fibers bonded to an elastic matrix. Two possible modes of microbuckling were assumed, that is the shear mode and the extensional mode. The shear buckling mode is predicted for all practical cases and the compressive strength has the simple evaluation $\sigma_c = \bar{G} \cong G_m / (1 - c_f)$, where c_f is the fiber volume fraction (see also Greszczuk, 1982). The experiments that followed Rosen's analysis consistently found compressive strengths much lower than the ones predicted by the model. Lager and June (1969) suggested a knock-down factor of 0.63 which made Rosen's model predictions fit their experimental data on boron/epoxy laminates. A more sophisticated modeling of a 2-D array of unidirectional equally spaced fibers in an elastic foundation was done by Chung and Testa (1969), Maewal (1981), Steif (1987) and Waas et al. (1990), among others. 3-D modeling was independently done by Sadowsky et al. (1967) and Herrmann et al. (1967). A new approach to microbuckling based on the inplane stability analysis of a single phase but periodically inhomogeneous solid has recently been undertaken by Lagoudas et al. (1991). Compared to previous modifications of Rosen's analysis, this last approach introduces bounds on the compressive strength, the upper bound being Rosen's result, while the lower bound being a substantial reduction from it, closer to experimental observations.

In many fibrous composite systems with softening matrices, the localization of the compressive failure leads to fiber kinking, eventually fracturing the fibers. A kinking type of compressive failure was experimentally observed, among others, by Broutman (1967), Chaplin (1977), Hahn and Sohi (1986) in various resin matrix composites, Evans and Adler (1978) in graphite matrix composites, and Yugartis and Sternstein (1988) in thermoplastic matrix composites. By using a simple model, Argon (1972) found the compressive strength to be proportional to the shear strength (as compared to the shear

modulus in Rosen's model) and inversely proportional to the maximum initial fiber misalignment angle for composite systems undergoing kinking compressive failure. Budiansky (1983), by incorporating a combined stress plasticity model, took into account a nonzero inclination of the kink band, extending thus Argon's analysis. He also gave an analytic evaluation of the kink inclination and the kink width. Recent work by Fleck and Budiansky (1990) and Steif (1990) addresses the elastoplastic problem of kink formation.

In this paper, an energy approach, that has been used in fracture mechanics for studying crack propagation, is applied to model compressive failure due to a steady state kink band propagation in fibrous composites. For a fixed grip experiment, where the boundary tractions produce no work, the steady state kink propagation assumption leads to a comparison between the strain energies of an unkinked strip of the composite with the same strip after it is fully kinked. The difference in the strain energies, which is equated to the dissipated work in the kink process zone, strongly depends on the geometrical constraints. Approximate fields are obtained through a shear lag model and used for the evaluation of the strain energies of the laminates studied. The current work presents an evaluation of the compressive strength for laminated fibrous composites that explicitly takes into account the geometry of the microstructure (fiber diameter, fiber spacing), the macro-geometry (lay-up configuration, ply thickness, gauge length) and the applied loading. The model predictions for the compressive failure due to kinking are compared with the microbuckling analysis results for various composite systems.

2. ANALYTICAL MODEL

As observed experimentally, especially in systems like carbon fibers – thermoplastic matrix, kinking forms in a fashion similar to that shown in Figures 1 and 2, where the fibers start rotating while the matrix softens and deforms along with them. Eventually, the fibers break in a brittle manner overloading and causing neighboring fibers to kink, giving rise to a kink band propagation. This process starts at some weak point along the specimen width, W , typically at one of the edges, and spreads throughout the width. We are interested in the energy balance of the laminate as the kink propagates a distance (ΔS) under fixed grip conditions, which is a reasonable assumption considering the relatively large kink propagation velocity with respect to the grip motion. Assuming that the width of the specimen is large compared with the kink length, l_k , so that the fields far upstream and downstream of the kink front are not affected by the kink formation zone, the principle of virtual work (Budiansky et al., 1986) under steady state conditions becomes

$$U_u - U_d = (2 A_f g_f + \frac{1}{4} d_f \sigma_{ym} l_k^2 \alpha_k) N \quad (1)$$

In the above A_f , d_f are the fiber cross sectional area and diameter, respectively; g_f is the energy released per unit area corresponding to flexural breaking of the fibers (fiber toughness) and is evaluated experimentally; σ_{ym} is the matrix yield stress; l_k , α_k are the kink zone length and rotation, respectively (Fig. 1); N is the number of fibers crossed by the kink band as it propagates a distance (ΔS) (Fig. 2).

The first term on the right hand side of (1) represents the work done to break all fibers crossed by the kink band as it propagates. The second term represents the amount of work dissipated in plastically deforming the matrix due to the large rotation of the fibers in the kink process zone. This term is found following a similar derivation for the plastic work dissipated in a shear kink formation by Evans and Adler (1978). The left hand side of the equation represents the decrease in strain energy of the specimen due to kink propagation assuming that there is no flux of strain energy into the system from the boundary. The evaluation of the upstream strain energy is straightforward and is given by

$$U_u = \frac{\bar{\sigma}^2 \Delta S L T}{2 E} \quad (2)$$

under uniaxial loading. In the above equation $\bar{\sigma}$ is the overall applied stress at the far upstream side of the specimen; T is the total thickness of the specimen; E is the effective axial stiffness of the laminate.

The evaluation of the downstream strain energy, U_d , in (1) is carried out using a shear-lag model (Hedgepeth, 1961, Lagoudas et al., 1989) as shown in Fig. 3. The figure shows the intact layers attached on both sides of the kinked layer, each representing one or more plies in the actual laminate with thicknesses, $h_i, i=1,2,3$. The kinked ply transfers its axial compressive load to the intact plies through matrix shear layers of thickness t . The equilibrium equations in terms of displacements can be written as

$$\frac{d^2 v_1}{dy^2} - \left(\frac{G}{t}\right) \left(\frac{v_1 - v_2}{E_1 h_1}\right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d^2 v_2}{dy^2} + \left(\frac{G}{t}\right) \left(\frac{v_1 - 2v_2 + v_3}{E_2 h_2}\right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d^2 v_3}{dy^2} + \left(\frac{G}{t}\right) \left(\frac{v_2 - v_3}{E_3 h_3}\right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where v_i , $i=1,2,3$, denote the axial displacements of the plies. The model is subjected to displacement boundary conditions at $y=\pm L/2$ to simulate a strain controlled experiment. At $y=0$, the axial displacement of the intact plies is zero, while a condition of zero axial stress in the middle ply is enforced to reflect the substantial weakening due to kinking. The shear parameter G/t , which represents the stiffness of the shear layers, is not adjusted to reproduce experimental results but is assigned values that reflect the geometry and material properties of the tested specimens. Assuming a rectangular array of fibers, the assigned value is given by

$$\frac{G}{t} = \frac{1}{d_f} \frac{G_m}{\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4c_f} - 1}} \quad (6)$$

where G_m is the matrix shear modulus. It should be noted that the shear-lag model does not include any bending effects that might occur due to out-of-plane kinking, as shown in Fig. 1. The simplicity in the modeling is justified by the fact that the information obtained from the shear-lag model will only be used qualitatively in this work.

3. RESULTS

The proposed model is used to predict the compressive strength of flat specimens under direct compression. Fig. 4 shows the configuration and loading of the specimens used by Yurgartis (1987), Yurgartis and Sternstein (1988) and Lee (1987) in a scaled down IITRI fixture. The specimens used by Yurgartis and Sternstein were made of (AS-4) carbon fibers in polycarbonate (PC) matrix. Lee tested similar specimens with different gauge lengths.

3.1 Effect of gauge length on compressive strength While all other parameters are kept constant, specimens of different gauge lengths are analyzed. The gauge lengths used are 6.0, 12.0 and 26.0 mm. Fig. 5 shows the predicted strengths for a $(0)_{12}$ unidirectional laminate assuming that only one of the middle plies is kinked ($h_1/h_2/h_3=5/1/6$, see Fig. 3). The material properties used are $E_f=233$ GPa, $E_m=2.4$ GPa, E is found by the rule of mixtures for fiber volume fraction $c_f=0.52$ and $g_f=22$ N/m. For the three values of matrix shear modulus reported in Fig.5, that is $G_m=600,660,710$ MPa, the values for the matrix yield strength are $\sigma_{ym}=37,51,63.5$ MPa, respectively. These three different values correspond to compression tests carried out at three different temperatures (Yurgartis, 1987). The microgeometry is defined by taking $d_f=6.85 \mu\text{m}$, $l_k=10d_f$ and $\alpha_k=67^\circ$. The evaluation of l_k is based on experimental

evidence and analytical estimates (e.g., Budiansky, 1983), while the estimate for α_k is derived by Evans and Adler (1978). The results reported in Fig. 5 indicate that lower strengths are expected as the gauge length increases. Although the properties of materials used by Lee are not available, the analytical predictions are qualitatively in agreement with his findings on the effect of gauge length.

3.2 Effect of the Number of Kinked Plies For the results to follow, the gauge length is fixed at 6.0 mm to represent specimens used by Yurgartis (1987). The analytical results obtained when varying the number of damaged plies are shown in Fig. 6. In the figure, the layup ($x/y/z$) denotes the number of plies in each of the three axial layers of the shear lag model, namely (y) denotes the number of kinked plies and ($x+z$) is the number of intact ones. In the extreme case, (0/12/0), all layers are damaged and the corresponding downstream strain energy U_d in (1) is taken to be zero. In this particular case the analysis is simpler, since there is no need for the shear lag model, and the predicted compressive strength can be given in closed form by

$$\bar{\sigma}_c = \sqrt{\frac{2c_f E}{\pi d_f L} (\sigma_{ym} \alpha_k l_k^2 + 2\pi d_f g_f)} \cong \sqrt{\frac{2c_f E}{\pi d_f L} \sigma_{ym} \alpha_k l_k^2} \quad (7)$$

For most composite systems the dissipated plastic work is much larger than the work spent in breaking the fibers and the approximate formula given above may be used for the compressive strength evaluation. This is certainly the case for carbon/thermoplastic systems. Fig. 6 shows that as the number of damaged plies increases, the stress required to propagate the kink band decreases, therefore implying that the kink band will first grow across the thickness of the specimen and it will subsequently propagate along its width. This is in accord with Yurgartis and Sternstein experimental observations and with analytical results by Fleck and Budiansky (1990). It is to be noted that (7) gives a conservative prediction of the compressive strength with respect to the experimental results of Fig. 6.

3.3 Comparisons between kinking and Microbuckling A new approach to compressive strength due to microbuckling in fibrous composites has recently been proposed by Lagoudas, Tadjbakhsh and Fares (1991). It is based on elastic inplane stability analysis of inhomogeneous anisotropic materials and it substantially reduces the Rosen analysis prediction for the compressive strength. Actually the upper bound is exactly Rosen's formula, that is $\sigma_c = \bar{\sigma}$, while the lower bound for the compressive strength is given by

$$\sigma_c = \bar{G} \frac{1 + \frac{\Delta E}{2\pi E} \sin(\pi c_f) [\cos(\pi c_f) - \sqrt{\cos^2(\pi c_f) + 8}]}{1 + \frac{\Delta E}{2\pi E} \sin(\pi c_f) [2\cos(\pi c_f) - \frac{4\Delta E}{\pi E} \sin(\pi c_f)]} \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta E = E_f - E_m$. For the particular case of 50% fiber volume fraction and large stiffness ratio, E_f/E_m , the above formula reduces to $\sigma_c = \bar{G}/(1 + \sqrt{8}/\pi) = 0.53 \bar{G}$. The comparison of the compressive strength due to kinking as predicted by equation (7) with the compressive strength due to microbuckling according to (8) is shown in Fig. 7 for a carbon/PC-thermoplastic and boron/epoxy unidirectional composites. Fig. 7a implies that the kinking failure mode is more likely to occur for the carbon/thermoplastic for all fiber volume fractions, while Fig. 7b suggests that for a wide range of fiber volume fractions (10%–70%) the microbuckling failure mode is more likely to occur for the boron/epoxy composite. The material parameters for the carbon/thermoplastic system are reported in Section 3.1, with the experimental value for the compressive strength being equal to 770 MPa. The material parameters for the boron/epoxy system are taken from Lager and June (1969) and they are $E_f=400$ GPa, $E_m=3.4$ GPa, $G_m=1.3$ GPa, $\sigma_{ym}=45$ MPa, $d_f=120$ μm . The experimentally measured compressive strengths for boron/epoxy are very close to the microbuckling analysis results (Lagoudas et al., 1991). It is to be noted that even though the effective shear modulus of the boron/epoxy system is larger than the shear modulus of the carbon/thermoplastic composite, the substantially larger boron fiber diameter results in higher kinking compressive strength, rendering microbuckling the failure mode for the boron/epoxy composite. This becomes clear from (7) if we take l_k to be proportional to d_f .

4. CONCLUSIONS

The model presented in this paper is capable of predicting the compressive strength due to kinking for fibrous composite laminates under in plane loading. The model is not restricted to unidirectional composites and different layups are currently being investigated. The comparison between compressive failure due to kinking and microbuckling brought in the importance of the matrix yield strength in addition to the matrix shear modulus, de-emphasized the importance of the fiber volume fraction dependence and introduced explicitly the fiber diameter influence. An important conclusion is that kinking failure depends on material as well as structural parameters, while microbuckling failure depends on material and microstructural parameters only.

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Fig. (1): Kinking Under Axial Compression.

Fig. (2): Kink Propagation.

Fig. (3): Shear Lag Model.

Fig. (4): Configuration and Loading of Test Specimen.

Fig. (5): Effect of Gauge Length on Predicted Strength.

Fig. (6): Comparison Between Experimental and Analytical Results.

Fig. (7): Comparison of the Compressive Strength Due to Kinking and Microbuckling.

